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Research Article

**IMPORTANCE OF CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN THE
TREATMENT OF ACUTE NONCOMPLICATED
APPENDICITIS**¹Dr Asim Khan, ²Dr Syeda Mahrukh Shakir, ³Dr Mubashir Bhutta¹Saidu Medical College, Swat/Saidu Group of Teaching Hospital²Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur³Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To evaluate the role of non-operative management of acute non complicated appendicitis in terms of its cost effectiveness and associated morbidity and mortality.

Venue and Duration: This prospective observational study was conducted at the surgical Unit-II of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from September 2019 to September 2020.

Methodology: The study included 100 unselected patients with early acute uncomplicated appendicitis, diagnosed on the basis of clinical history and examination supported by laboratory tests. Of the 100 patients, 65 received intravenous antibiotics for two days followed by oral antibiotic therapy for 7 days, while 35 control patients were randomized to surgery. The data was collected in the forms developed for the study. Patients were monitored and monitored for the course of various diseases.

Results: There were 65 men and 35 women with an average age of 20. Right iliac pain associated with nausea, vomiting and anorexia were common symptoms, while fever, tachycardia and rebound tenderness in the right iliac fossa were common symptoms. The patients were randomly divided into two groups. Group 1 (treated conservatively) improved after a quiet stay of 2 to 4 days. Relapse occurred in 6 operated patients. Postoperative complications occur in only one patient. The period of stay in the hospital was 3 to 6 days. In group 2 (treated with surgery), one patient had a perforated appendix with an appendix. Postoperative complications developed in six patients. The stay in the hospital lasted from 4 to 9 days. In our study, no mortality was observed in both groups.

Conclusion: Patients treated conservatively with antibiotics experienced mild pain with less pain medication. While morbidity, mortality and surgery costs are all avoided, the relapse rate is not insignificant.

Key words: acute appendicitis, conservative management, relapse

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INTRODUCTION:

Reginald Filz first described acute and chronic appendicitis in 1886. As the most common cause of acute abdomen worldwide, males between the ages of 10 and 20 are commonly affected but can occur at any age.

Although lumen obstruction is essential for gangrene of the appendix and appendicitis perforation, many other factors have been reported as causative agents of mucositis and lymphoid hyperplasia, such as an infectious agent, possibly a virus. Seasonal fluctuations in incidence are also observed.

Migrating pain with movement or coughing, nausea, vomiting, and anorexia are classic symptoms, while fever, tachycardia, local tenderness, cover and rebound tenderness in the right iliac fossa are the results of the study. Various gastrointestinal, urological, gynecological, as well as other metabolic, neurological, and malignant causes of abdominal pain can be included in the differential diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

Clinical evaluation and experience supported by various evaluation systems such as the Alvarado system are the main tools for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

Urinalysis, complete blood count, ultrasound-assisted C-reactive protein, computed tomography (CT) scans, and diagnostic laparoscopy are useful tests.

Once diagnosed, treatment options include treatment including antibiotics or an appendectomy, preferably laparoscopic, but population assessment has identified a significant long-term risk for appendicitis testing. Small bowel obstruction requiring surgery has been shown to occur in 1.3% by 30 years, and mortality within 30 days is 0.24% with increased standard mortality. Also, a negative appendectomy is particularly difficult with problems. The aim of this study was to evaluate the role of conservative treatment in the treatment of acute appendicitis in unselected patients and to demonstrate that antibiotic therapy is as safe and effective as appendectomy in the treatment of acute uncomplicated appendicitis.

METHODOLOGY:

This prospective observational study was conducted at the surgical Unit-II of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from September 2019 to September 2020.

A total of 100 patients with early acute uncomplicated appendicitis were recruited. The diagnosis was made

on the basis of a typical interview, clinical examination supported by laboratory tests and confirmed by operational results. All patients presenting later than 24 hours were excluded from the study, as well as patients with abdominal pain for reasons other than acute uncomplicated appendicitis. Depending on the treatment method, patients were divided into two groups.

Sixty-five patients in Group 1 were selected for maintenance therapy in which no oral medications, intravenous fluids, and antibiotics were administered (3rd generation intravenous cephalosporin plus metronidazole for two days, followed by oral antibiotics for another 7 days), and 35 patients in Group 1 2 underwent emergency appendectomy using the conventional method as a control group. The patients were carefully monitored for any complications and disease course. The conservatively treated subjects were discharged within 12-24 hours and followed for 6 months. Study variables such as treatment regimen, symptom relief, disease relapse, postoperative complications, and postoperative hospital stay were analyzed to determine their effect on outcome.

RESULTS:

The age ranged from 15 to 30 (mean: 20). Sixty-five (65%) patients are male and 35 (35%) patients are female (M: F = 2: 1). Common symptoms were abdominal pain located in the right iliac fossa (100% of patients), nausea and vomiting (91% of patients) and anorexia (79% of patients), fever (81% of patients), pulse rate > 90 / minute (71% of patients) and rebound tenderness in the right iliac fossa (67%) were common symptoms. White blood cell counts greater than 11,000 / mm³ were found in 87 (87%) patients.

Patients from group I (65%), treated conservatively, had no complications and were discharged after a hospital stay of 2 to 4 days. Four (6%) patients relapsed within 4 months and 2 (3%) patients relapsed within 6 months. They underwent appendicitis by the conventional method. Postoperative complications were wound infection in only one (16%) patient. The hospital stay lasted from 3 to 6 days.

In the group of 2 patients (35%) treated with conventional appendectomy, one patient (2.8%) had appendix perforation / gangrene with appendix. Postoperative complications were wound infection in 3 (8.5%) patients, pelvic removal in one (2.8%) and subsequent obstruction of the small intestine (adhesive) in 2 (5.7%) patients. The stay in the hospital lasted from 4 to 9 days.

No other pathology, such as appendicitis carcinoid, was observed in any of the patients of the two groups.

Table 1: Clinical features

Clinical features	Number of patients	Percentage
Symptoms:		
Pain right iliac fossa	100	100
Nausea/vomiting	91	91
Anorexia	79	79
Signs:		
Fever	81	81
Tachycardia	71	71
Rebound tenderness	67	67
Leucocytosis	87	87

Table 2: Postoperative complications

Complications	Group-1 (recurrent cases) Number of patients (%)	Group-2 Number of patients (%)
Wound infection	1 (16%)	3 (8.5%)
Pelvic collection	0 (0%)	1 (2.8%)
Adhesive small bowel obstruction	0 (0%)	2 (5.7%)

DISCUSSION:

In our study, males outnumbered females with an average age of 20, which is consistent with the findings of Styruud J et al. In our study, 65 patients with acute uncomplicated appendicitis that occurred within 24 hours were treated with antibiotics. They had improved earlier and their stay in the hospital was smooth. Various studies have looked at the role of treating acute uncomplicated appendicitis. Spontaneous resolution of early acute appendicitis may occur and treatment, including antibiotics, may be an alternative to surgery.

We use third-generation cephalosporin and metronidazole in all patients treated conservatively. Many effective combination antibiotics have been developed over the past decade and the availability of monotherapy to effectively treat intra-abdominal infections has made triple antibiotic therapy obsolete. In our study, six (9%) patients returned with a recurrence of prior signs and symptoms. They were

sent for surgery. Reported rates of recurrent appendicitis have ranged from 6 to 14% over several small series. Another randomized study comparing appendectomy to antibiotic therapy in men aged 18 to 50 years found that 88% improved without surgery and 14% had recurrent appendicitis within one year.

We observed that only one (16%) of the 6 patients with recurrent appendicitis developed postoperative wound infection. The reported rate of complications after appendectomy after conservative treatment ranges from 2% to even 23%.

In group 2, perforation of the appendix with faeces was found in one patient (2.8%). Despite the increased diagnostic accuracy and the shortening of the time interval between presentation and appendectomy treatment, the perforation rate in acute appendicitis has remained the same since the 1980s, at around 20–30%. Postoperative complications occurred in six (17.1%) patients treated surgically in our study. The overall

postoperative complication rate is approximately 10–19% for non-perforated acute appendicitis and 12–30% for perforated appendicitis.

Population assessments revealed significant long-term risks associated with surgical exploration of appendicitis. Therefore, recently there is a growing interest in antibiotic therapy as the primary treatment. The results of our study confirm the above protocol.

CONCLUSION:

Patients with a brief history of abdominal pain, localized tenderness, and hemodynamic stability can be managed non-surgically as this is cost effective and eliminates the mortality and morbidity associated with routine appendectomy.

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